

BIOMIMETIC AEROGELS FROM MICROFIBRILLATED CELLULOSE AND XYLOGLUCAN

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SUMMARY

Cellulose aerogels with density of 7–100 kg/m³ were prepared by freeze drying from microfibrillated cellulose water suspensions, and biomimetic aerogels were prepared with the addition of xyloglucan. Their microstructures and physical properties were characterized by scanning electron microscopy, nitrogen adsorption measurements, and tensile tests.

Keywords: Microfibrillated Cellulose, xyloglucan, aerogels, mechanical properties, biomimetic composites.

INTRODUCTION

Aerogels refer to a new class of materials holding air in their structure. They are highly porous solids having a large inner surface area. They are extremely light, low heat conductive, and high sound absorbent materials. Therefore, aerogels have excellent performance in applications such as heat insulators, particle filters, particle trappers, and catalyst carriers¹. Aerogels are prepared starting from gels by carefully replacing the liquid by air while the structure is maintained. This is mostly done by supercritical drying or freeze drying. Most of the aerogels have the drawback of being brittle, and this considerably limits their applications, and only a few non brittle aerogels could be found in the literature²⁻⁴.

Microfibrillated cellulose (MFC) is a nanoscale, fibre like material prepared by microfibrillation from wood pulp generally⁵⁻⁸. Because of its high stiffness, high aspect ratio, and numerous hydrogen bonds, microfibrillated cellulose has shown the ability to form a highly entangled network characterized by high mechanical properties⁹, to reinforce starch foams¹⁰, and to form low density flexible aerogels⁴.

Since MFC is obtained in an aqueous suspension, freeze drying technique is a simple and environmental friendly route for the solvent removal in preparing MFC aerogels. Freeze drying consists of freezing the suspension and then sublimating the ice under low pressure. The capillary forces are avoided and the structure is preserved to a large extent.

In this paper, we present interesting features of microfibrillated cellulose aerogels, in particularly, their compression mechanical properties where they show a ductile behaviour characterized by a high kinetic energy absorption ability and good thermomechanical properties. A biomimetic approach for the preparation of composite aerogels using microfibrillated cellulose and xyloglucan is also presented. The properties of the aerogels are significantly improved by mimicking the primary plant cell wall structure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

The microstructure of the MFC aerogel having a density of 7 kg/m^3 was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and a highly porous structure was observed as shown in Figure 1. Individual cellulose microfibrils formed a 3D network structure. The nitrogen adsorption isotherm of the MFC aerogel was of type IV according to IUPAC classification (Figure 2), *i.e.* multilayer adsorption onto a mesoporous solid with strong adsorbent-adsorbate interactions. The specific surface area was $35 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ by the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) analysis.

Figure 1. SEM micrograph of the MFC aerogel with a density of 7 kg/m^3 (Scale bar, $5 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure 2. Nitrogen adsorption (open symbol) and desorption (solid symbol) isotherms of the MFC aerogel with a density of 7 kg/m^3 .

Compression mechanical properties

The results of the compression mechanical properties of MFC aerogels with different densities are summarized in Table 1 in terms of energy absorbed. By varying the density of

the aerogels, it is possible to obtain a wide range of mechanical properties with the energy absorbed ranging from 92 to 930 KJ/m³. The MFC aerogels are also found to be highly compressible, thus to foster applications in many ways such as packaging and protection, which are not possible for the brittle inorganic aerogels

Table 1. Energy absorption of MFC aerogels with different densities (taken as the area below the stress strain curve up to a strain of 70%).

MFC aerogel density (Kg/m ³)	28	60	100
Energy absorbed (KJ/m ³)	92	419	930

Thermomechanical properties

The thermomechanical properties of the MFC aerogels were characterized by dynamic thermal mechanical analysis (DMA) and the MFC aerogels maintain their storage modulus in the range of 1.6–3.5 MPa even at 300 °C.

Biomimetic MFC and xyloglucan composites

To mimic the primary plant cell wall structure, biomimetic aerogels consisting of microfibrillated cellulose and xyloglucan (XG) were prepared, the aim was to study the effect of the addition of xyloglucan on the mechanical properties of the aerogels and relate it to their microstructure. Interestingly, MFC/XG aerogel with a density of 4 Kg/m³ was successfully prepared, which is among the lightest aerogel in the literature. The SEM micrograph of the MFC/XG aerogel having 43% of XG is shown in figure 3. The presence of XG in the aerogel allowed a finer structure compared to pure MFC aerogel. Indeed, less aggregated cellulose microfibrils was observed.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of MFC/XG aerogel having 43% of xyloglucan (Scale bare, 5µm).

The results of the mechanical tests are summarized in Table 2. The MFC/XG composite aerogels exhibited much higher compression mechanical properties compared to MFC aerogels. This is probably due to the fact that xyloglucan links the adjacent cellulose microfibrils together to form a much resistant load bearing network, and the “pillars” effect provided by the microfibrils in the presence of xyloglucan.

Table 2. Energy absorption of MFC xyloglucan composite aerogels (density, $21\pm 1\text{kg/m}^3$).

XG in MFC aerogel (%)	0	10	20	30
Energy absorbed (KJ/m^3)	55,5	70,7	82,9	104

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